

Design and Evaluation of a Scaled Electromagnetic Damping Module for Optimized Active Vibration Control in Rail Systems

Sripaadh Jayashree Kuppusamy
Wakeland High School
sripaadhj@gmail.com

Abstract – Rail systems for transportation are often subject to high levels of vibrations, which are detrimental to passenger comfort and structural integrity. This work presents the design, implementation, and characterization of a scaled electromagnetic damping system that translates real-time displacement measurements into proportional magnetic damping forces via a closed-loop PD control system. A PWM-driven electromagnet, with a soft iron core, is characterized by duty cycle values ranging from 5% to 95% and reveals nonlinear onset of effective actuation consistent with magnetization behavior. Experimental results characterize the spatial field distribution and PWM-to-field relationship, informing a control law that addresses the nonlinear relationship between actuation current and damping force.

Index Terms - Electromagnetic damping, active vibration control, PWM modulation, magnetic levitation, PD control

I. INTRODUCTION

The use of magnetic levitation in transport has been a concept since the 1960s and has been in operation since the 1980s. The captivating nature of magnetic levitation systems for rail-transport stems from its utilization of magnetic forces to suspend and propel vehicles. Unlike traditional wheeled transport, magnetic levitation systems almost eliminate the effect of friction [1].

The modern applications of magnetic levitation typically follow two paths: Electrodynamic Suspension (EDS) and Electromagnetic Suspension (EMS). The main difference between the two methods is that while EDS uses

repulsive forces and superconductivity, EMS uses attractive forces of electromagnets. The most famous applications of magnetic levitation for transportation can be found in East Asian countries, such as China and Japan. Specifically, China's Shanghai Transrapid and Japan's upcoming Shinkansen are world renowned magnetic levitation systems. These systems allow people and goods to travel at great speeds, nearly 600 kilometers per hour [3].

Though these systems are famed examples of technological advancements, they have their own shortcomings. Specifically, magnetic levitation systems have the issue of low-frequency vibrations and lateral swaying [1]. In a levitating state, a vehicle lacks the physical damping provided by contact with surfaces, which makes it susceptible to oscillations. This is an issue to be considered due to its wide range of effects. At a low level, these oscillations can cause passenger discomfort and/or motion sickness. At a higher level, they could pose significant safety threats.

Therefore, methods to reduce these lateral vibrations and swaying need to be found. One such way is using an active control system that uses magnetic damping and PID to provide dynamic damping. By continually adjusting the dynamic corrective forces (produced by electromagnets) based on real-time measurements, active systems can suppress oscillatory motion effectively. The active vibration control method is often superior to passive vibration control due to its ability to change the magnitude of corrective forces at high speed based on the application and the specific scenario.

Therefore, this study investigates how PWM duty cycle influences magnetic field strength and damping behavior

in a scaled electromagnetic system, and how this relationship can inform active vibration control strategies.

The objective was to design, simulate, and prototype a scaled active damping module capable of translating displacement measurements into proportional magnetic forces. While this specific module does not operate at the scale of levitating full-size rail vehicles, it provides the fundamentals of control systems that take rapidly changing feedback to provide proportional electromagnetic damping. Additionally, this scaled model provides the logic system, which is scalable to any other size, as well as system integration.

The current hypothesis is that increasing PWM duty cycle will result in a nonlinear increase in magnetic field strength, leading to enhanced damping behavior due to stronger induced electromagnetic interactions.

This work presents a data-driven nonlinear mapping between PWM duty cycle and magnetic field strength in a soft-iron core electromagnet and demonstrates its integration into a closed-loop proportional-derivative control framework for active vibration control. Unlike linear approaches, the nonlinear approach adheres to the nonlinear relationship between current, magnetic field, and the resulting damping force.

II. METHODS

I. System Overview

The damping module is designed to demonstrate the principles of proportional electromagnetic damping for magnetic levitation systems. The module is a closed loop, modular system that converts displacement measurements into controlled magnetic forces. The system architecture is composed of three primary subsystems: control, power electronics, and actuation. On their own, these subsystems are optimized for high-speed responses and come together to create an integrated unit.

The closed-loop module was preferred over an open-loop module mainly due to the lack of flexibility of the open-loop module. To ensure the efficacy of the system, it was imperative that the module was responsive to even unexpected disturbances in vibration. Therefore, the closed-loop design was an obvious choice.

Furthermore, the system's timing capabilities are critical. This warranted the operation of microcontrollers and sensors at a kilohertz-level for response rates.

II. Control Subsystem

The control subsystem is built around the Arduino Uno R3 microcontroller. This microcontroller is an 8-bit AVR-RISC device chosen due to its high-performance features at a low power rate. It is preferred because of its use of the ATmega328P. Specifically, the ATmega328P also has 6 PWM channels (which can technically enable the use of multiple electromagnets) and UART, which allow for efficient debugging and telemetry independent of PWM output. These features are also extremely important for being able to take in information while simultaneously updating the duty-cycle without overloading the CPU with CPU-cycle contention.

Displacement is measured with a HCSR-04 ultrasonic sensor, which is able to provide high-frequency readings of a target position relative to the sensor. The measurements are input into the microcontroller, which executes a proportional-derivative algorithm allowing for the seamless translation of distance measurements into PWM duty cycles.

The proportional mapping of the magnetic field is governed by the following idea:

$$I_{coil} \propto f(d) = \begin{cases} I_{max}, & d \leq d_{min} \\ I_{idle} + kP(e(t)) + Kd \frac{de(t)}{dt}, & d_{min} < d < d_{target} \\ I_{idle}, & d \geq d_{target} \end{cases}$$

where I_{coil} is average current that the electromagnet receives, d is the measured displacement according to the HCSR-04 sensor, and I_{max} and I_{min} correspond to the maximum and idle electromagnet currents, respectively. The kP and kD terms are used as per the PD Control equation. As per the theory, kP is the proportional gain, and kD is the derivative gain. $\frac{de(t)}{dt}$ is the rate of change of the error with respect to time. Constraints are also placed on the duty cycle such that the coil current remains within the confines of safe operation limits and prevents excess mechanical stress on instruments.

The PWM signal generated by the microcontroller is used to modulate the MOSFET in the power electronics subsystem by controlling the average current through the electromagnet and varying it proportionally to displacement. An initial OCR value is set in the microcontroller code, which is then continuously updated in response to dynamic input.

III. Power Electronics

The power electronics subsystem interprets the PWM output of the microcontroller to drive the electromagnet. This is done using a logic-level N-channel MOSFET by using it as a pseudo-switch to determine how much current should be sent into the electromagnet depending on the distance from the wall. The maximum current that can be sent through the electromagnet is dependent on the characteristics of the coil as well as the number of turns. Considering that the soft iron rod diameter is about 0.5 inches, the resistance in an electromagnet that uses 20 AWG enameled copper with ~270 turns could have around 0.3-0.7 ohms of resistance. For the scaled model, this would result in a maximum current of about 3 Amps. Controlling maximum current is critical for system integrity and to ensure that the coil does not overheat.

The implementation of a flyback diode is imperative in such a module. This diode is placed across the coil to protect the MOSFET from spikes in voltage when the coil turns on or off rapidly. Without the use of this component, the MOSFET would experience immense inductive kickback when the magnetic field of the coil collapses, which could result in the MOSFET frying.

IV. Actuation

Actuation is the final subsystem of the unit, which takes all the data collected and results in a magnetic field of corresponding magnitude. As mentioned prior, the electromagnet is manufactured using a copper coil and a soft iron core. The use of the soft iron core is deliberate due to its high magnetic permeability, which allows for the concentration of the magnetic field. This magnetic field will interact with the conductive rail to induce eddy currents. Due to Lenz's Law, the eddy currents also create magnetic fields that oppose the motion of the conductive target, generating damping forces [2].

The interaction between these fields results in a localized increase in magnetic pressure ($P_{mag} = \frac{B^2}{2\mu_0}$).

This pressure is mathematically represented as the Maxwell Stress Tensor, which results in the restoring force that is exerted on the train [1].

In the context of this system, a full tensor analysis is beyond scope due to the simplified nature of a scaled-down model and the simplified geometry of the electromagnet and conductive target. However, the scalar nature of magnetic pressure and its derivation provide insight into the main relationship: as magnetic strength

increases, pressure increases, which results in a restoring force that scales with the square of the magnetic field.

The implication of this relationship has heavy effects on the PWM aspect of this module. Because the restoring force is related to the square of the field, linear interpolation is not appropriate ($F \propto B^2 \propto I^2$). Instead, the PWM calculation must be done with PD control, such that even a small change in B results in a large change in force.

V. Experimental Design

To determine the validity of this module, a controlled experiment is designed. Using a version of the module on a breadboard, I held objects at varying distances from the HCSR-04 Ultrasonic Sensor to initiate the control loop. In order to ensure that the magnetic field from the electromagnet is behaving accordingly to the distance measured through the ultrasonic sensor, an SS49E hall effect sensor is brought to the electromagnet to determine the strength of the magnetic field generated. In order to make sure that the hall effect sensor readings are accurate and consistent, it is imperative that the hall effect sensor is held at a constant distance away from the electromagnet.

The data collected from this experiment is plotted on a graph to determine the nature of the relationship that exists between distance from the ultrasonic sensor and the magnetic field. Using methods of regression, the approximate equation, and hence the relationship between the two parameters, can be seen. Further, the ideal orientation of the electromagnet can be determined by comparing the peak magnetic field strength for select orientations.

It is also important to note that in this set up, the magnetic field is likely lower than that of an ideal electromagnet due to the inevitable imperfections associated with handmade parts.

III. RESULTS

To evaluate the performance of this particular set-up of an electromagnetic damping module, experimental data was collected to characterize the relationship between PWM duty cycle, magnetic field strength, and theorized damping behavior. The data provides insight into a non-linear relationship between distance and magnetic field strength and the non-linear nature of electromagnetic actuation in general.

I. PWM Duty Cycle vs. Magnetic Field Strength

To determine how control input impacts magnetic actuation, voltage output from the SS49E Hall Effect Sensor was recorded for PWM duty cycles ranging from 50 to 950. These voltage measurements were converted to magnetic field strength, in Gauss, using a linear calibration model based on the nominal sensitivity and offset of the sensor. The resulting data is compiled into Table 1.

TABLE I
EFFECT OF PWM DUTY CYCLE ON FIELD STRENGTH

Duty Cycle vs Voltage Reading and Field Strength		
Duty Cycle	Voltage Reading	Field Strength (G)
50	2.44	43
100	2.44	43
150	2.44	43
200	2.44	43
250	2.44	43
300	2.44	43
350	2.44	43
400	2.44	43
450	2.4	71
500	2.37	93
550	2.36	100
600	2.35	107
650	2.35	107
700	2.29	150
750	2.25	179
800	2.24	186
850	2.24	186
900	2.12	271
950	1.92	414

This data reveals a distinct nonlinear relationship between PWM Duty Cycle and magnetic field strength. At low duty cycle values (50-400), the measured magnetic field strength stays at a value of ~43 Gauss.

This plateau is an indication of the fact that there does not exist a meaningful increase in magnetic field strength with an increase in PWM values within this range. Physically, this means that the current supplied to the electromagnet is not adequate to sufficiently magnetize the soft iron core.

Beyond a PWM Duty Cycle value of about 450, a transition becomes apparent. In this region, the voltage begins to decrease, indicating an increase in the magnetic field strength. This behavior reflects the onset of effective electromagnetic actuation, where sufficient current flows through the coil to induce stronger magnetization within the soft iron core. At higher PWM values, around and above 750, the magnetic field strength increases rapidly. At 95% duty cycle, the magnetic field strength magnitude reaches values above 400 Gauss. This region is characterized by nonlinear increases in field strength, with small changes in PWM resulting in large increases in field strength.

II. Spatial Distribution of Magnetic Field

To investigate how the magnetic field changes with distance, measurements were taken at multiple distances away from the electromagnet, while keeping the duty cycle constant. Finer measurements were made, meaning magnetic field was measured at smaller increments between 5 and 30 mm.

The data, shown in Table 2, shows a rapid decrease in magnetic field strength as distance away from the coil increases. The voltage readings rise from about 2.38V at 5 mm to around the nominal voltage ~2.47V starting at 25 mm. The steep slope near the coil indicates that the magnetic field is highly concentrated in the regions closer to the source of the field, which is consistent with established models of magnetism ($1/r^3$) [2].

TABLE 2
EFFECT OF DISTANCE ON FIELD STRENGTH

Distance vs Voltage Reading and Field Strength		
Distance	Voltage Reading	Field Strength (G)
5	2.38	85.7
10	2.41	64.3
15	2.43	50
20	2.44	42.9
25	2.47	21.4
30	2.47	21.4

III. Data Analysis Through Regression Models

Using Python libraries including numpy, scipy, sklearn, and matplotlib, the data collected in tables 1 and 2 were run through a regression model to determine appropriate equations.

It was decided that the data from Table 1 would be fit using an exponential model, as it describes data that is increasing and concave up. Unlike $\frac{1}{r^2}$ or $\frac{1}{r^3}$, which are both concave up but decreasing, an exponential model fulfills both requirements. An important distinction to be made is that while the exponential model may fit the data in Table 1, it is still not the ideal theoretical model. This is because it is the nature of a soft iron core to require a stronger magnetic field to magnetize and reach maximum magnetization before 100% duty cycle is reached. Therefore, at PWM values approaching closer to 1000, the second derivative of the function should begin to decrease. These behaviors fit an S-curve rather than an exponential model.

That said, due to safety concerns, the maximum PWM value that was tested was 950, at which the data still seems to be concave up. For these reasons, an exponential model was chosen.

For table 1, it was found that the data fit the equation $B = 0.0843 \cdot e^{0.00864x} + 90.31$ (figure 1), with an R^2 value of 0.957. Therefore, the equation is an extremely strong fit as this regression function accounts for almost 96% of variations in the data.

Fig. 1. Magnetic Field Strength vs. PWM Duty Cycle

As for table 2, the data fits the equation $B = 253.53 \cdot x^{-0.645}$, with an R^2 value of almost 0.907 (Figure 2). Though this is lower than that of the equation for the data in Table 1, the fit is still rather strong, as the R^2 value suggests that the regression equation accounts

for 91% of variations in the data. Additionally, contrary to idealized theory, the decay for this extended solenoid was slower than that of a point dipole due to the fact that the distances measured were still in what is considered the near-field of the electromagnet.

Fig. 2. Magnetic Field Strength vs. Distance From Electromagnet

Beyond magnetic field strength, validation of the system also depends on the force created by eddy current damping. This is the main aspect of the module that governs vibration control. Therefore, using the eddy current damping force approximation $F = \sigma t w B^2 v$, where σ is the electrical conductivity of aluminum, t is the conductor thickness, w is the conductor width, B is the magnetic field strength, and v is the target velocity, the theoretical eddy current forces were determined according to the field strength values for the active duty cycle region. The following constants were assumed for a scaled aluminum conductor target: $\sigma = 3.5 \times 10^7 \frac{S}{m}$, $t = 3\text{mm}$, $w = 50\text{mm}$, and $v = 0.05 \frac{m}{s}$. The results were plotted on a graph (Figure 3), which shows that the damping force too increases nonlinearly. That is, the rate of change near PWM = 500 was low whereas the rate of change was much higher later on, near PWM = 900. The forces ranged from 13.23 mN at PWM 450 to 449.91 mN at PWM 950. This corresponds to a 34-fold increase in damping force magnitude, demonstrating strong nonlinear amplification of actuation efficiency with increasing PWM values. These forces arise from the induced eddy currents opposing the motion of the conducting target (i.e. the train), consistent with Lenz's Law.

Fig. 3. Eddy Current Force vs. PWM

III. Simulation and Dynamic Validation

To evaluate and validate the performance of the proposed damping module in the absence of large-scale conductive materials, a simulation-based evaluation was conducted. To conduct this simulation, a second-order mass-spring-damper system was used to model vibration:

$$m\ddot{x} + c\dot{x} + kx = 0$$

where m represents the system mass, k is the magnetic stiffness, and c is the damping constant. Using the established equation for the approximation of eddy current force, the values of a baseline damping constant and a maximum damping constant were found. The damping constant was modeled as a function of magnetic field strength such that it is proportional to the square of the field strength. For the scope of the simulation, the values for k , baseline c and m were 50, 0.1, and 0.5 respectively.

The chosen values were used due to reasonable assumptions of the characteristics of a scaled prototype and environment. For a damping module of such size, it was assumed that a reasonable mass for the conductive target could be 0.5 kg. The choice for the value of k was a representative estimate for magnetic stiffness in a small-scale system, pending experimental characterization. The baseline damping coefficient value was determined with physical reasoning. Even for a system without any electromagnetic damping, some damping will exist due to real world phenomena, such as air resistance, thus warranting a non-zero value for c .

The two scenarios, a minimally damped system and a maximum damping system, were tested. The results of the simulation are shown in Figure 4.

Fig. 4. Displacement vs. Time for Different Damping Scenarios

The results of the simulation present significant improvement in vibrational stability with the inclusion of electromagnetic damping. The minimally damped system exhibited sustained oscillatory behavior with noticeable, yet minimal reductions in vibration amplitude over the simulated time frame. In contrast, the damped system exhibited a rapid decrease in displacement, with the vibration amplitude reducing to less than 5% of its initial value within 1 second. As duty cycle was decreased, the time taken to approach an amplitude of 0 increased. The rapid approach to near 0 of the damped system in contrast to the sustained oscillations of the minimally damped system confirms that increases in control input, through their nonlinear effect on magnetic field strength, translate directly into improved vibration suppression.

IV. DISCUSSION

In order to tackle the issue of low-frequency lateral vibration, a scaled down damping module was designed using an Arduino, an HCSR-04, and other accessory parts. In order to use the data given by the HCSR-04, a Proportional-Derivative (PD) control architecture was developed using C++. Linear interpolation was used initially but was replaced with PD Control to adhere more closely to actual magnetic field behavior. PD control was chosen over the conventional PID control due to PD control's fast response speed, increased stability, and smoother motion.

The performance of the scaled down model was gauged through experiments that examined how magnetic field strength varied with the change in certain parameters. Specifically, the variations in magnetic field were examined for changes in PWM duty cycle and

distance away from the electromagnet at a constant duty cycle. The data collected was run through a Python regression program and plotted using matplotlib, which revealed expected behavior of field strength increasing rapidly with a small increase in PWM and decreasing according to a power model with an increase in distance. Regression analysis yielded $B = 0.0843 \cdot e^{0.00864x} + 90.31$ ($R^2 = 0.957$) for the PWM-to-field relationship and $B = 253.53 \cdot x^{-0.645}$ ($R^2 = 0.907$) for the spatial decay. These behaviors confirmed the control system and logic, which is imperative for the next step of scaling up.

Future iterations may use the ATtiny841 microcontroller and the VL53L1X ToF sensor for improved timing precision and will include direct damping validation using aluminum targets. Additionally, prototype-level printed circuit boards may be printed. The governing damping relationship relies more heavily on magnetic field strength and conductor interactions rather than system size. Therefore, this model remains valid under geometric scaling, provided the field intensity and conductive surface area are proportionally maintained. This supports the applicability of the proposed system to full-scale rail operations. However, the inevitable scaling up will use drastically different parts that can handle more stress and higher voltages, such as FPGAs and IGBTs in place of the current microcontroller and MOSFET.

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